

Reading Note – Histoire de l’Iran 2

- INALCO – EUUB420b – Histoire de l’Iran 2 – Reading Note
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Article 1 : “*Iran's Policy Towards Afghanistan*” by Mohsen M. Milani (2006), *Middle East Journal*, Vol. 60, No. 2), pp. 235-256.

Article 2 : “*Damming Afghanistan: Modernization in a Buffer State*” by Nick Cullather (2002), *The Journal of American History*, Vol. 89, No. 2, pp. 512-537.

1. Authors and Articles

Mohsen Milani (PhD in political science, University of Southern California) is a Tehran born foreign policy analyst and professor of politics. He is the Executive Director of the Centre for Strategic & Diplomatic Studies and Professor of Politics at the University of South Florida. He has served as a fellow at Harvard, Oxford, and Foscari University. His most famous book is “*The Making of Iran’s Islamic Revolution*”. He is active in talks and hearings before governmental administrations and the US Congress as an expert in Iranian studies.

His text describes Iran’s foreign policy regarding Afghanistan and its key interests and motives and its long-term approach and attitude regarding Afghanistan’s internal unrest, political tensions and foreign interventions. His analysis focuses on contemporary events occurred after the downfall of the Afghan monarchy and especially the USSR withdrawal. He stresses the remarkable continuity of Iranian policy in favour of Afghanistan’s stability.

Nick Cullather (PhD in political science, University of Virginia 1993) is an American historian and professor of history at Indiana University and was an editor of the *Journal of American History*. He is specialised in the US diplomatic history and intelligence, development, and nation-building. His most famous books are “*Secret History: The Classified Account of its Operations in Guatemala, 1952-54*” based on declassified CIA documents and “*Illusions of Influence: The Political Economy of United States-Philippines Relations, 1942–1960*”.

His text describes over forty years the advent of a US led hydroelectric and irrigation dam project in the Helmand Valley. He explains how this US and Afghan governmental development project failed both technically, socially and environmentally because of political stubbornness and

diplomatic face saving. He gives details of the many consequences and issues raised by this project's multiple changes of tack.

2. Summary of article 1

"Iran's policy towards Afghanistan" by Mohsen Milani (Middle East Journal, 2006).

Introduction

Iran's foreign policy favours a stable and moderate Afghanistan with good inter-governmental relations and Herat as a buffer zone. Iran relies on a Shia and Persian speaking community, an anti-Taliban-Saudi-Pakistani resistance spirit and an economic sphere of influence. Iran's long-term objective is to become Afghanistan's transit hub for trade with the Persian Gulf, India and China. The Islamic Republic of Iran considers the United States as a massive existential threat and has developed asymmetric deterrence.

Creating an ideological sphere of influence (1979-1988)

Khomeini inherited a complicated relationship with Afghanistan consisting of a light and suspicious cooperation under Moscow's threatening shadow. Iran offered lip-service resistance to the 1979 Soviet invasion, yet hosting 1,5m Afghan refugees. Meanwhile the American hostage's crisis put Iran and the USA at loggerheads and Iran's priority focused on victory in its war with Iraq.

Iran used the Afghan Shia minority but refrained fuelling Muslim unrest in Afghanistan in a bargain between Moscow's military assistance to Iraq and Soviet protection at the UN security council against US wrath. Iran was highly suspicious of the Saudi, Pakistani and US support of the Afghan Mujaheddin. Iran resented the Saudi support to Iraq and to Wahhabi ideology in southern and Central Asia, while the US turned a blind eye on the aftermath of fostering extremist Islamic groups.

Creating a political sphere of influence (1989-1996)

Unable to control Afghanistan, the USSR left in 1989 a power vacuum filled with proxy wars of neighbouring countries. Saudi's objective was to expand its Wahhabi influence. Pakistan's was to control a Pashtun dominated government. Iran's was to prevent foreign influence in Afghanistan and to promote Iran as trading hub and route for Central Asia.

Iran called for national reconciliation and multi-ethnic governance as an alternative to the Saudi and Pakistani backed Pashtun hegemony. To Iran's delight, a loose coalition of Uzbek Rashid Dostum and Tadjik Ahmad Shah Massoud took control of Kabul in 1992 replacing Najibullah's orphan regime. But peace and stability stumbled because of warlordism and hostility of Saudis and Pakistanis who used Gulbuddin Hekmatyar as their Pashtun champion.

Iran was overwhelmed by the Afghan situation complexity and failed in keeping the Afghan government and military groups in line with a consistent political alliance. Civil war erupted in 1992-1993 with heavy casualties and destructions in Kabul. Amid hell, the Taliban rose to power.

Helping create a sphere of resistance against the Taliban (1996-2001)

The Pakistani secret services helped the Taliban grow from a small religious Pashtun students' group to a dominant political and military movement, ferociously opposed to Shi'ism. Pakistan and Saudi Arabia swapped Hekmatyar for the Taliban and generously funded them as a warhead against a crumbling and divided Afghan government. Iran seemed unsuspecting of the rising threat of a Sunni Pashtun fundamentalist theocracy. The Northern alliance and the Afghan Shi'ites did not oppose a united front and Iran's allies Abd Al-Ali Mazari of the Shia Hezb-e Whadat and Ismail Khan of Herat were soon impeached. In 1996, the Taliban entered Kabul.

Iran refused to recognise the Taliban government and continued supporting the Northern alliance, without engaging in direct military action. Iran feared flows of refugees and criticized Taleban ideology and "narco-terrorist" activities. Afghanistan became a proxy battleground opposing Iran to Saudi Arabia and Pakistan. Saudis and Pakistanis tried portraying the Taliban to the US government as a stabilising force and reliable countercheck to Iran and worked together on a gas pipeline project, bypassing Iran, and linking Turkmenistan to the Indian ocean. Iran and the Taliban came close to open war when Iranian diplomats were taken hostages and killed, a reminiscence of the 1979 US embassy crisis in Tehran. Finally, after 09/11/2001, the Taleban blind support to al-Qaida triggered the US invasion and the end of Taliban rule.

The fall of the Taliban and US-Iran competition in Afghanistan

The fall of the Taliban came as a gift to Iran. Iran was first in condemning the 09/11 attack. Pakistan turned side immediately and got lavish advantages from the US. Saudi Arabia was unscathed although 15 out of 19 plane terrorists were nationals. Iran hoped for a rapprochement with the Americans on grounds of military cooperation and oil industry opportunities and started cooperating with American advisors in Afghanistan and participated actively in the 2001 Bonn conference.

But in January 2002, President Bush included Iran in its “Axis of Evil” shortly after Israel seized a Palestinian cargo loaded with Iranian weapons. Iran officials started criticising US presence in Central Asia and warned against future escalation in Iraq. Nonetheless, despite reciprocal bellicose rhetoric, Iran stuck to its stabilisation policy in Afghanistan.

Iran and Afghan reconstruction, Herat and the US

Iran kept good terms with Karzai interim government, while maintaining its support to the Northern Alliance and consolidating its influence around Herat. It promoted with discretion a US withdrawal and fought drugs inflows to Iran. But three issues remained : Afghan refugees in Iran, US troops presence and the ongoing Turkmenistan pipeline bypassing project. Additionally, Iran resented Karzai’s pashtounisation policy, the marginalisation of warlord close to Iran and the lack of control on narcotraffic which destabilised Iran’s border provinces.

Iran’s ambitions as trade hub for Central Asia with the Herat region as a pivot induced heavy Iranian investments in Afghan infrastructures reconstruction, especially in international road connections with Tajikistan and Uzbekistan. Its objective was to offer landlocked Afghanistan an alternative to Pakistan with the Iranian sea harbour of Chabahar.

Herat was Iranian until 1857 and Iran considers it as a legitimate buffer zone to be protected from internal Afghan conflicts. Under warlord Ismail Khan, Herat’s trade with Iran was prosperous under discreet presence of Iranian authorities and a tacit non-aggression pact with US forces. Despite Hamid Karzai efforts to regain centralised control of the country and to thwart local warlords, Iranian growing influence was not significantly challenged.

Ahmadinejad and Afghanistan

The invasion of Iraq in 2004 took priority over Afghanistan. As a paradox, US interventions relieved Iran of two geopolitical threats and helped Tehran build a powerful Shia influence in Iraq.

Ahmadinejad presidency raised nuclear contentions with the West. He also enacted an “Islam-centered” foreign policy, reminiscent of the 1980’s Islamic revolution mantra. Yet, Iran’s general policy regarding Afghanistan remained unchanged but with a stronger insistence on US withdrawal.

Meanwhile, the unstable situation in Iraq has enticed the Taliban to rise again. Despite open animosity between Iran and the US, Mohsen Milani concludes that Iranian general policy and strategy towards Afghanistan should likely remain the same.

Conclusion

As opposed to its otherwise aggressive foreign policy, Iran has proved remarkably constant and moderate regarding Afghanistan and supported the same Afghan groups that were ultimately sponsored by the US. Shared objectives are a stable Afghanistan, riddance of the Taliban and the fight against narco-traffic. Iran nervosity lies in the US massive military presence in its immediate vicinity. But Iranian leaders must bear in mind that Iran has a lot more to lose in an open conflict with the US and should choose dialogue and negotiation.

3. Summary of article 2

“Damming Afghanistan: Modernization in a Buffer State” by Nick Cullather (The Journal of American History, 2002).

Introduction

In 1949, President Harry Truman announced a “Point Four” development programme targeted to third world countries. At the time, modernisation and technical education were linked with nationalism in newly erected nations.

The Helmand Valley project in Afghanistan lasted from 1946 until 1976 and enjoyed continuous comprehensive US leadership, financial and technical support. Because of its size, technical ambition and duration, the project required considerable impetus and efforts supported by US-born concepts and mindsets, estrange and sometimes unsuitable to Afghan culture.

The accidental nation

Curzon defined Afghanistan as a political void between Persia, Russia and British India, populated by diverse ethnic groups with Pashtun predominance. The British Raj devised in 1893 a fortified frontier “the Durand line” to split the Pashtun tribal zone cohesiveness and keep at bay potential Russian invaders. The British partially secured indirect control over Afghanistan using the Pashtun royal clan as a client monarchy. British India also helped build a fictional Pashtun racial and warrior supremacy over other ethnic minorities in Afghanistan such as Tajiks, Hazaras, Uzbeks and Baluchis. But the royal Afghan government was weak with very limited fiscal resources and reliable means of communication to project central authority outside Kabul.

Zaher Shah sought foreign nations’ help, mainly Germany, to modernise key infrastructures, create embryos of state-controlled industries, trade and fiscal laws to build the basics of statehood control. After WW2, America replaced Germany as western patron of Afghanistan whose chief export

commodity was Astrakhan sheep wool. Much to Afghanistan disappointment, the British Raj collapse in 1947 did not end the fictitious Durand line partition between Pashtun tribes with newly formed Pakistan. During the next 20 years, the Pashtunistan controversy dragged Afghanistan's diplomacy in trade and border conflicts with Pakistan and in a slow rapprochement with the USSR. But the USA retained a major role in consolidating the monarchy's legitimacy and centralisation policy through modernisation projects such as the Helmand Valley Dam.

A Tennessee Valley Authority for the Hindu Kush

During the mid-twentieth century, hydro-electric dams bore huge significance. It symbolised collective effort to the greater good and the leading role of the state in public planning and modernisation. The US public works company Morrison Knudsen was selected to build a dam downstream of Kabul and upstream of Kandahar at the junction of Helmand and Arghandab rivers. It would regulate a versatile (1 to 30 times) water flows in a once fertile valley before the Mongol invasion destroyed its irrigation system.

Drawbacks such as silt deposit in the upstream reservoir preventing rejuvenation of downstream fields, capillary salination of the downstream riverbed and soil exhaustion due to heavy irrigation with poor drainage were not acknowledged at the time and did not weigh much in the face of renewable electricity resources, employment, roadworks perspectives and national pride and prestige.

Very soon, salt emerged around the dam work. But the Helmand dam had become an international showcase for American development programmes. This duplication in Afghanistan of the New Deal Tennessee river Valley Authority was meant to outflank the communist land distribution promises. From 1946 onward, the Helmand and Arghandab Valley Authority drained most of Afghanistan treasury, soaked investments and agricultural revenues of the Afghan population. The project evolved to a gigantic series of canals, tunnels, pipes, drains, reservoirs and secondary dams which required ever more population displacement and land expropriations.

In 1957, brutal snow meltdowns in the Hindu Kush nearly broke the main dam, soil salination accelerated and reservoir ice-cold waters altered agricultural products output variety. Despite its alleged technical failure, the HAVA project became entangled in a vast social science "proof of concept" laboratory in the desperate pursuit of adaptative and overtime changing objectives. HAVA became too big to fail.

A strange kind of Cold war

US officials relied on the royal court westernised educated elite, like PM and king cousin Mohammed Daoud. They thought they had the right people to manage social change without triggering revolution. These Afghan technocrats were pushing an all-out defensive development programme to preserve independence from greedy neighbours. The HAVA project became a key asset of American influence and credibility in Afghanistan. It was presented as a mean to settle down transborder nomadic Pashtun herders between Kabul and Kandahar, but this social engineering project was opposed with strong resistance despite financial and real estate enticements. Systematically, Daoud's central government favoured Pashtun interests and ideologically disregarded US advisers' attempts to overcome interethnic rivalries or to include Mullahs as key intermediaries and advocates for new agricultural techniques.

In 1955, Khrushchev's USSR entered a competition spree with the USA on subsidies and investment projects for Afghanistan development and industrialisation. In 1959-1960, famines in the communist bloc allowed the US to boast about their economic model. Meanwhile, the Helmand project proved increasingly a financial and social strain for Afghanistan and a complete failure, with actual crop yields dropping below pre-dam standards. The US wouldn't give up nor confess because their whole credibility was at stake.

Under the Kennedy-Johnson administration, USAID thought a new impetus could be engaged with "Green revolution", mass education and new agricultural techniques. These concepts proved very hard to implement because they required a complete reverse engineering of land property and layout with regular, levelled, non-obstructed, standardised patches of land. Bulldozing and forced displacements of whole villages were met with violent resistance against the HAVA agricultural experts.

During the 1960s, PM Daoud stepped down and ethnic, religious and political oppositions enjoyed larger freedom of speech and started criticising the lack of progress in economic and agricultural developments and the burden of foreign debt on inefficient, ill-thought governmental projects.

The 1971-1973 "El Nino" meteorological effect ruined hopes in the "Green revolution" take-off. The Helmand reservoirs dried up and the USSR-USA détente relaxed the need for competitive benefactor spendings. Helmand valley crop yields were 45 times lower than in Iowa and below average with the rest of Afghanistan. HAVA was a complete failure and the US finally pulled out to a lingering stop in 1978.

In 1973, Daoud led a coup against the king amidst general civil unrest because of food shortages. In 1978, another coup led by the pro-soviet Khalq party also failed to stabilise the country. A menacing Islamic takeover triggered the 1979 Soviet invasion. During the anti-Soviet war (1980-1988), Helmand became a battlefield, rigged with minefields, drawing its population in exile to Pakistan.

The Taliban movement thrives well in Helmand and Kandahar. Opium poppies grow well in saline and dry soils and Helmand's share in heroin world production is now 39%. Ironically, the Taliban finalised an unfinished US hydroelectricity plant project in 2001 on one of Helmand dam, months before it was bombed by the American air force.

Conclusion

The HAVA project failed because water scarcity was identified as the sole problem to agricultural productivity. The project was managed like a nation-changing and promethean masterwork from a purely engineering, technical and economical viewpoint. It had scarce to no considerations for its complex and multi-layered consequences on social, political and environmental issues. The human factor was systematically underestimated, ignored or misjudged. The premises of the project were built on wrong development theories such as the superiority of settled wheat farmers over nomad pastoralists. Positive outcomes such as increased tax revenues, political stability of Pashtuns, increased agricultural revenues were considered mere by-products of the HAVA projects and not legitimate objectives per se. The HAVA project survived over 30 years after its early obvious failure because successive Afghan governments and US administrations recycled it overtime as a polymorphic flagship to changing modernisation purposes and political goals.

4. Personal Comments and Critic - Conclusion

Mohsen Milani's text is a wide and comprehensive overview of Afghanistan's recent history from an Iranian strategic interest's perspective. He insists on the constant endeavour of Iran to maintain a peaceful, stable and "poppy-free" Afghanistan and to promote a multi-ethnic and multi-religious balance of power as opposed to Pashtun hegemony.

These constant and general strategic objectives are complemented by two economical long-term ambitions. Iran wishes to stand as a trade and logistic hub for Central Asian land locked countries and to be considered as the natural sea link between them and the Indian Ocean and Persian Gulf. Also, Iran wishes to maintain a specific sphere of influence on the Herat region, historically bound to Persia.

Iran fears and opposes three menaces. Iran is suspicious of the Pashtun-Taliban hybris for solitary power against the other minorities (Tajiks, Uzbeks, Hazaras, Baluchis) because it fears waves of refugees. Iran is suspicious of foreign interventions whether from Saudi Arabia for parochial Wahhabi proselytism or from Pakistan for complex historical and ethnic reasons with their “manipulate and divide the Pashtuns” policy.

Additionally, Iran fought against the Great Game’s modern version in Afghanistan between the USSR and the USA. It opposed the USSR occupation from 1979 to 1989 with whatever energy its war with Iraq left Iran with. The US invasion in 2001 and overthrow of the Taliban received a lukewarm welcome from Iran, but much to its dismay, Iran was soon cornered by the Bush administration in the “Axis of Evil”. Ever since, Iran has kept a prudent attitude with the Afghan Pashtun dominated government, while insisting rhetorically on American military withdrawal.

Mohsen Milani concludes his analysis in 2006, long before the US withdrawal in 2021. He insists on shared US-Iranian geopolitical long-term interests on Afghanistan despite their mutual antagonism. He warns Iran that it has more to lose opposing the USA than coming to an understanding with them.

Nick Cullather’s text is focused on the Helmand Valley hydroelectric and irrigation project over a 30-year period. He describes how this huge technological infrastructure work was sponsored overtime by the USA for strategic and diplomatic reasons and how the Pashtun dominated Afghan government supported it as a sleeping-partner out of national pride and prestige and for the sake of modernisation ideology.

Well after it became obvious that the project was a technical, economic and environmental disaster, the US and Afghan governments proceeded with stubbornness, adapting the original objectives to immediate constraints raised by the project flaws. New assignments were given to the project such as irrigation, increasing agriculture productivity, settling Pashtun nomadic tribes, starting a Green Revolution etc. New methods and techniques were put in place without any considerations to Afghan cultural, social and political real-life issues. A debauchery of money, technical and engineering advice were poured overtime on this emblematic project. But the problem grew ever bigger to the point that the successive coups d’état at the end of the 1970s gave the US the pretext for withdrawing altogether from this promethean project failure leaving the Helmand to disheartened would-be Taleban and poppy cultivation.

In my opinion, Nick Cullather’s article gives a good summary of the main characteristics of Afghanistan historical and ethnic complexities. It gives a very interesting analysis of the quite specific HAVA project and suggests a more general US cumbersome behaviour in handling the

complex social, cultural and political situations in Afghanistan. One cannot but make a parallel with the blind stubbornness of US in applying “one size fits all” solutions in its foreign involvements, duplicated “from the book” by US think tanks in Afghanistan (and later without hindsight in Iraq). One cannot but make a parallel between the Helmand project on a provincial basis and the US government failed attempt to transform multi-ethnic Afghanistan into a centralised western style democracy. Among other things, the former pretended to reform the nomadic Pashtun way of life and the whole region agricultural economy. The latter tried building-up its army into a US style organisation heavily dependent on air support and intelligence technology. Salination left barren lands and the US military sudden withdrawal left Kabul to the Taliban offensive. He also shows how the the Pashtun relative majority was favoured because of their reputation as the natural leading group in Afghanistan. Cullather shows inadequate western global solutions were to complex polymorphic Afghan issues.

Mohsen Milani’s article underlines a much subtler attitude and awareness of Iran towards its neighbour’s complex history and society. It shows how Iran stucked to limited key objectives (Herat, trade routes, stability) and chose to interfere only on a few variables (Northern Alliance, coexistence with the US) leaving such “nation-building” concepts to US experts. Milani’s paper does not give general background of the shared history of Iran and Afghanistan and their cultural commonalities which could help understand the cautiousness and the keen mutual comprehension between both countries. He shows how Iran has favoured a more realistic approach in support of minorities to balance the Pashtun majority while the US let Karzai and Ghani governments disarm provincial militias for the sake of a theoretical centralised governmental army which proved ineffective when it came to defend the regime in faraway Kabul.